

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some of the Rare Earths. La(III), Pr(III) or Nd(III)-CDTA-Hydroxy Acids

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Formation constants of the mixed ligand complexes, MAL, [where M=La(III), Pr(III) or Nd(III); A=1,2-diaminocyclohexanetraacetic acid (CDTA) and L=Pyrocatechol (PY), disodium salt of 1,2-dihydroxybenzene-3,5-disulphonic acid (Tiron) and disodium salt of 1:8-dihydroxynaphthalene-3,6-disulphonic acid (CS)], have been determined potentiometrically at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. The values for the mixed ligand formation constant K_{MAL} have been found to be lower than the formation constant K_{MA} (where MA=1:1 binary complex). The difference in the value of K_{MAL} and K_{MA} can be explained on the basis of electrostatic repulsion and the basicity of the ligand involved. In all the systems studied, the value of K_{MAL} follows the order: La(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III).

In earlier communications from these laboratories, potentiometric studies of the biligand systems, Ln(III)-CDTA-IMDA, HEDTA or EDTA and Ln(III)-EDTA-IMDA, NTA or HEDTA have been described¹⁻². However, pH-metric studies of the interaction of hydroxy acids with 1:1 Ln(III)-CDTA systems do not appear in the literature. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to carry out detailed studies of these investigations and the results are discussed in the present paper.

Experimental

The chemicals used during these investigations were of analar grade. The rare earth oxides were of spectral grade and a stock solution was prepared and standardized as reported in earlier communication². The tripotassium salt of CDTA (Koch light, England, pure) was prepared by dissolving its known amount in the required volume of 0.1M KOH. The solutions of PY (E. Merck, pure), Tiron (E. Merck, pure) and CS (Fluka, pure) were prepared by dissolving their calculated amounts in doubly distilled water. These were standardized potentiometrically against 0.1M potassium hydroxide solution.

The pH-metric titrations were carried out with a Cambridge pH-meter, standardized against 0.05M potassium hydrogen phthalate solution at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. The following pH-metric titrations were carried out:

System: Ln-CDTA-PY.

- 10 ml (0.025M) PY (curve a, Figs. 1 to 3).
- 10 ml (0.025M) tripotassium salt of CDTA in presence of 10 ml (0.025M) Ln-nitrate [Ln-CDTA, 1:1] (Curve b, Figs. 1 to 3).
- 10 ml (0.025M) tripotassium salt of CDTA in presence of 10 ml (0.025M) Ln-nitrate and 10 ml (0.025M) PY [Ln-CDTA-PY, 1:1:1] (curve d, Figs. 1 to 3).

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titrations of La(III)-CDTA-PY; Tiron; CS ternary systems, (a) PY; (a') Tiron; (a'') CS; (b, b', b'') 1:1 La(III)-CDTA; (d) 1:1:1 La(III)-CDTA-PY; (d') 1:1:1 La(III)-CDTA-Tiron; (d'') 1:1:1 La(III)-CDTA-CS; (c, c', c'') corresponding composite curves of mixed systems. m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion.

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations of Pr(III)-CDTA-PY; Tiron; CS ternary systems. (a) PY; (a') Tiron CS; (b, b', b'') 1:1 Pr(III)-CDTA; (d) 1:1:1 Pr(III)-CDTA-PY; (d') 1:1:1 Pr(III)-CDTA-Tiron; (d'') 1:1:1 Pr(III)-CDTA-CS; (c, c', c'') corresponding composite curves of mixed systems. m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion.

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titrations of Nd(III)-CDTA-PY; Tiron; CS ternary systems. (a) PY; (a') Tiron; (a'') CS; (b, b', b'') 1:1 Nd(III)-CDTA; (d) 1:1:1 Nd(III)-CDTA-PY; (d') 1:1:1 Nd(III)-CDTA-Tiron; (d'') 1:1:1 Nd(III)-CDTA-CS; (c, c', c'') corresponding composite curves of mixed systems m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion.

Similar sets of titrations were carried out for Ln-CDTA-Tiron and Ln-CDTA-CS systems respectively. The ionic strength of all the solutions was kept constant by using 0.1M KNO_3 solution. The total volume was raised to 50 ml in each case and an inert atmosphere was maintained by passing oxygen free nitrogen gas.

Results and Discussion

Curve a, a' and a'' (Figs. 1 to 3) represent the potentiometric titrations of PY, Tiron and CS respectively. The values of acid dissociation constants of these acids were taken from the literature^{3,4}. Curve b, b' and b'' (Figs. 1 to 3) corresponds to the titrations of binary mixtures of 1 : 1 Ln-CDTA, which exhibit inflexions at $m=1$ (m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion). These curves indicate the formation of 1 : 1 Ln-CDTA simple chelates due to the neutralization of the free proton of the carboxylic group of CDTA. The titration curves d, d' and d'' (Figs. 1 to 3) clearly show a lower buffer region in comparison to the 1 : 1 simple systems and this lowering can be due to the formation

of a new ternary species. The superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve⁵ in the lower buffer region supports the stepwise formation of the mixed complexes in each case and the secondary ligand is attached only after the complete formation of 1 : 1M-CDTA binary complex. Their formation constants K_{MAL} have been calculated by the method of Thompson and Loraas⁶.

Systems. M-CDTA-PY, Tiron.

When the equimolar systems M-CDTA-PY, Tiron (curve d and d', Figs. 1 to 3) are titrated, two inflexions at $m=1$ and $m=3$ are observed. The first inflexion at $m=1$ may be due to the formation of 1 : 1 M-CDTA binary chelate. Further addition of the alkali neutralizes the hydroxylic protons of the PY or Tiron and an inflexion at $m=3$ may be attributed to the formation of the mixed complex (MAL). The appearance of the green colour in case of PY and yellow colour in case of tiron after $m=1$, clearly indicates the existence of new species. After $m=1$, a lower buffer region starts clearly

showing the formation of the mixed complex between $m=1$ to 3 and this can be further substantiated by comparing the curves d and d' (Figs. 1 to 3) with the corresponding composite curves c and c'.

From table 1, it may be noted that the value of K_{MAL} increases from La(III) to Nd(III). This trend can reasonably be explained⁷ on the basis of the increasing complexing power of the rare earth ions as the atomic number increases.

TABLE 1. FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES

$\mu=0.1M$ KNO_3 , $t=30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$

L	$\text{Log } K_{\text{La-CDTA-L}}^{\text{La-CDTA}}$	$\text{Log } K_{\text{Pr-CDTA-L}}^{\text{Pr-CDTA}}$	$\text{Log } K_{\text{Nd-CDTA-L}}^{\text{Nd-CDTA}}$
PY	4.83 ± 0.07	5.69 ± 0.07	6.10 ± 0.08
Tiron	5.86 ± 0.07	6.72 ± 0.05	7.08 ± 0.06
CS	6.70 ± 0.03	7.52 ± 0.03	7.95 ± 0.04

Systems. M-CDTA-CS.

Solutions containing equimolar concentrations of M-CDTA-CS on titration (Curve d'', Figs. 1 to 3) give three inflexions. In the beginning, 1:1 M-CDTA binary complex appears to be formed and further addition of the alkali gives a sharp inflexion at $m=2$ due to the neutralization of one of the phenolic protons of CS. The third inflexion at $m=3$ may be ascribed to the neutralization of the second phenolic proton of CS liberated due to its chelation with the simple (1:1) complex. After $m=2$, a lower buffer region starts clearly indicating the formation of the mixed complex. The formation of the mixed complex (MAL) between $m=2$ to $m=3$ may be further substantiated by the appearance of the pink colour and by comparing the curve d'' (Figs. 1 to 3) with the corresponding composite curve c''. The value of K_{MAL} of the resulting mixed complexes shows the same trend as discussed earlier and can be explained on similar lines.

It may further be observed that in all the above cases K_{MAL} has a lower value than K_{MA} . This can reasonably be explained on the basis of the electrostatic repulsion between the incoming charged hydroxy acid ion and the M-CDTA binary complex and the basicity of the incoming ligand.

A plot of $\text{Log } K_{MAL}$ against $\text{Log } K_{MA}$ ⁸ (Fig. 4, where A = CDTA) gives a straight line showing a linear relationship between the formation constants of the binary and ternary complexes. It can thus be concluded that the relative stabilities of binary as well as ternary complexes vary in the same order.

Fig. 4. A plot of $\text{Log } K_{MAL}$ VS $\text{Log } K_{MA}$
(1) M-CDTA-PY vs M-CDTA ;
(2) M-CDTA-Tiron vs M-CDTA ;
(3) M-CDTA-CS vs M-CDTA.

The possibility of the rare earth ions having coordination number more than six exists in these biligand complexes and this fact has been reported by previous workers⁹⁻¹¹ also. In terms of the secondary ligands, the formation constants of the resulting ternary complexes of any particular rare earth ion decrease in the following order :

The greater stability of the CS ternary complexes may be due to the presence of the naphthalene ring and the least stability in case of Pyrocatechol complexes may be due to the fact that the sulphonate groups in the case of Tiron and CS increase the reactivity of the aromatic hydroxyl groups towards coordination with the metal ions¹².

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References

- H. S. RANA and J. P. TANDON, *Bull. Acad. Polon. Sci.*, 1975, 3, 185.
- H. S. RANA and J. P. TANDON, *Monatsh.*, 1975, 106, 559.
- K. LAL and R. P. AGARWAL, *J. Less Common Metals*, 1967, 12, 269.

4. G. A. L. HEUREUX and A.E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 481.
5. G. H. CAREY and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2859.
6. L. C. THOMPSON and J. A. LORAAS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 89.
7. T. MOELLER, D. E. MARTIN, L. C. THOMPSON, R. FERRUS, G. R. FEISTEL and W. J. RANDAL, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **65**, 1.
8. MOELLER and FERRUS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **20**, 261.
9. G. ANDEREGG, P. NAGELI, F. MULLER and G. SCHWARZENBACH, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1959, **42**, 827.
10. H. IRVING and D. N. EDGIGTON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **21**, 169.
11. M. M. TAQUI KHAN and P. REDDY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 3.
12. G. H. CAREY, R. F. BOGUCKI and A. E. MARTELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1288.